

School's out for Redesign:

Involving Stakeholders in the Creation of a Teleclassroom Environment and Experience

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Abstract: In Teleclassing, a multidisciplinary research project, our partners set out to design and connect classrooms in such a way that those present at both locations would have the immersive, realistic experience of participating in a class together. To support the development of such an environment and the associated technology, which we called the teleclassroom, we held co-design sessions in which we asked students, teachers and other stakeholders to create their vision of the ideal teleclassroom. Conducting co-design to inform the design of actual environments is an innovative procedure and in this paper we will describe how we implemented it. We created a new toolkit to facilitate participants' thinking about the emotions and sensations that a teleclassroom should create, and how these experiences should be reflected in how the room is set up. Furthermore, we will describe what we learned from our sessions both with regard to conducting co-design for this purpose, and with regard to the development of the teleclassroom itself.

Key words: *e-learning, co-design, distance learning.*

1. Introduction

As a result of the Bologna Process, reforming academic education in Europe, and the increasing specialization in the academic field, more alliances are being made between and within universities. While this is likely to enhance the mobility of students and teachers, another contribution may come from new technology that allows improved remote interaction between universities. The Teleclassing research project aimed to realize the idea of a teleclassroom, which we defined as two university classrooms that are connected in such a way that teacher and students at both locations have an immersive and realistic experience of participating in a class together.

The idea of a teleclassroom is as attractive as it is complicated. While some of its advantages are obvious, it is also a huge challenge to recreate the interaction patterns and abilities from an offline educational setting. However, as Rowe [1] has put it, a teleclassroom should be designed in such a way that "interactions with remote people and environments are nearly the same as interactions with local people and environments." In order to realize this ideal, the project chose to focus on synchronized tele-education, because live instructions were found to catch students' attention and interest more easily than static materials [2].

The design of a teleclassroom entails both the design of an environment as well as an experience. If we want to understand what experience is desirable, however, we need to actively engage the stakeholders in the design process, so that a teleclass environment can be created that will fit people's practices. In other words, we need to apply a participatory design approach [3]. We chose a participatory design approach that requires a high degree

of engagement of the users, defined as co-design. Co-design is a form of co-creation (or "act of collective creativity that is shared by two or more people" (p. 2)) that is conducted in the course of a design process [4].

In the relatively new field of co-design, little attention has been paid so far to the co-creation of environments [5]. However, if the teleclassroom needs to support a human experience, we need to take into account the whole setting in which the experience takes place. It remains however unexplored how the experience end users look for in an environment can be translated to results with an architectural value. Our main challenge while preparing these sessions was that we needed to find a link between the methods used by architects to create environments (such as sketches, plans, perspectives, etc.) and co-design methods.

In this paper, we will explain how we involved both end users and experts in the design process of a teleclassroom and which methods we used to translate their needs and wishes into how they would like the future teleclassroom to look and feel.

2. Co-design sessions

The co-design sessions were done in the last stage of the Teleclassing project. Prior to this stage, a thorough understanding of current class experiences and practices was gained. This knowledge was gathered through class observations, interviews with teachers and student focus groups. The co-design sessions were organized to depart from the current reality and make stakeholders think about possible future realities in classrooms.

In what follows, we will describe which stakeholders participated in our research and which method we implemented to fully engage them in the creation process of the teleclassroom. The most straightforward group of stakeholders we involved are the end users, students and teachers who have direct, first-hand experience with what goes on in the classroom.

Apart from end users, i.e., teachers and students, we also asked other stakeholders to participate in our research. Both e-learning experts and architects were included for their expertise and indirect involvement in the future of the teleclassroom. Indeed, media-experts' opinion will bear on educational policies that will influence the take-up of new distance education technology and architects will help design the new classrooms the new technology.

We decided not to include designers in the co-design sessions. Although this approach has its merits (e.g., immediate involvement of the designer), we feared that including designers might bias the results of this complex exercise. Designers might (inadvertently) impose their professional vision on the other participants so that their input is lost. Therefore, we decided to let only the previously mentioned direct and indirect actors take part in the co-design sessions and to communicate the results of the sessions to the project partners afterwards.

Given the different background of the directly and indirectly involved actors, we needed to approach them differently and hence we organized separate sessions for both groups.

2.1 Participant Selection

- Direct actors

From the start of the project, it was fixed that students and teachers should be recruited from two universities of interest in Brussels and Ghent (VUB and UGent, respectively). Teachers were contacted personally through e-mail and through the newsletter of the VUB. Students were contacted through the VUB newsletter, personally and via teachers and we also recruited on campus by handing out flyers.

Preference was given to teachers that had experience with teaching in small groups, as the teleclass setup is targeted to catering relatively small groups. We made sure that participants had not been recruited in previous user research for the Teleclassing project, as we wanted the participants to take part in the sessions unbiased.

Recruitment proved to be very difficult, particularly the recruitment of the students. We learned that in many cases there is no interest to participate in research, regardless of an incentive, because students already feel over-demanded when it comes to research participation. Eventually, three students and four teachers (lecturers and teaching assistants) from the VUB effectively took part in one of the two sessions that we organized.

- Indirect actors

We recruited architects and experts in the field of distance education (either in terms of research or development). A call for participation for the architects was sent out in a newsletter of the 'Bond van Vlaamse architecten' and posted on the associated website. We also asked co-workers to contact architects they knew. The second group was contacted personally by mail and by telephone.

While we initially recruited five distance education experts, only one of these eventually participated in a co-design session, due to unexpected circumstances (work obligations and illness). Eventually we were able to organize two co-design sessions. In the first session, two architects participated together with a distance learning expert. In a second shortened session, two distance learning experts participated.

2.2 Procedure

The user research in the Teleclassing project was inspired by the contextmapping process, a procedure proposed by Sleeswijk Visser and colleagues [3] to map the contexts of people's interaction with products. The sessions we conducted can be seen as phase two and three of the process: the sensitization phase and (co-design) sessions. As noted earlier, two types of sessions were set up for the different actors. However, in essence, the sessions were structured similarly. After the introduction, participants were made more sensitive to the topic of the co-design sessions during an inspiration or sensitization phase. Next, participants started the co-design exercise, in which they could express their vision of the ideal teleclassroom (experience) collaboratively. A teleclassroom was neutrally defined as "a whole of two university classrooms at two different physical locations that are connected in such a way that a class can be taught and followed at both locations at the same time." Finally, the participants were introduced to the Proof-of-Concept (PoC) that was developed by our project partners. Participants were asked about their general response to the setup and what they saw as essential next steps for further development.

- The inspiration phase

The co-design sessions for the direct and indirect actors differed mainly with regard to the 'inspiration phase'. To ensure that the indirect actors would not only use their knowledge, but also take into account the experiences of the direct actors, they were first given a mind map of students' and teachers' current class experiences. This mind map was based on observations in classrooms and interviews with students and teachers conducted earlier in the project. Afterwards, we asked the indirect actors what they found remarkable about the mind map. We also inquired into the challenges and opportunities these actors believed the students' and teachers' remarks posed for a teleclass environment.

As direct actors have recent experience with giving or taking classes, we felt it was more appropriate to raise their awareness of their own expertise. We wanted them to reflect on the classroom environment, and think about how this environment may affect their class experience. Therefore, we asked them to sketch how a typical classroom they teach or follow classes in looks like. Then we asked them to discuss positive and negative experiences they had had in the classroom. The discussion generated insights into how these experiences were related to factors such as the shape of the classroom, the technology in the classroom, but also non-technological matters such as the interaction between those present in the classroom.

- The co-design exercise

When asking the participants to express their vision of the ideal teleclassroom, we emphasized that they should not merely think of what the two connected classrooms should look like, but also about the ideal experience that would play out in these rooms and how both are linked to each other. We also emphasized that we did not expect a detailed floor plan and that participants were able to present the result and motivate their decisions later on. We also informed them that a group compromise was not a requirement.

The participants received a 2D modeling kit to visualize their thoughts. This kit contained 2 large flipchart pages that allowed participants to both express the experience they are looking for and draw a setup of the teleclass setup. The content of this kit, created in collaboration with IBBT designer Pieter Heytens, is described in Table 1.

Table 1. Contents of the 2D modeling kit

Content	Description
2 large flipchart pages	<p>On these white pages the two classrooms could be visualized.</p> <p>A frame was drawn onto these white pages so that the inside of the frame could be used for visualizing the layout of the room.</p> <p>The margins contained words that reminded the participants of the experiential component of the modeling exercise ('emotions', 'sensations', 'interactions'). They also left room to paste words and pictures there that were relevant to the classroom experience; and to paste pictures of material that participants wanted on the walls, floor and ceiling.</p>
35 (material samples) + 61 (other) = 96 pictures	<p>This included both pictures of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Material samples for the walls, floor and ceiling - Pictures of different kinds of interaction - Objects - People <p>To each category, content was added that was either typical of the classroom (e.g. a desk) or non-typical (e.g. a plant)</p>
118 Words	<p>This included both words that described:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interaction styles - sensations
6 Classroom setup examples	Pages showing different potential formations of the desks in the classroom (e.g. auditorium setup, group work setup)
Open-ended material	White and colored A4 paper
Cutting, pasting and writing material	Scissors, glue, poster buddies, pens, crayons, felt-tip pens

The modeling exercise resulted in creations such as shown in Figure 1. Following the modeling, participants presented their ideal teleclass and motivated their decisions. In the session that involved two groups, the one group was asked to respond to the presentation of the other group and vice versa. In each session, the researchers asked the group to state what they saw as three core properties of the ideal teleclass environment.

Figure 1. Examples of results of modeling sessions

- Feedback gathering after introduction with Proof-of-Concept

At the end of the sessions, we introduced participants with the Proof-of-Concept (PoC) that was developed by our partners in the Teleclassing project. The indirect actors visited the actual setup in Ghent, while the direct actors saw video clips of the setup in use.

The setup of the PoC encompassed two rooms: a local site and a remote site. At the local site (where the teacher is physically present), an interactive whiteboard was installed on which the teacher could display and annotate teaching material. In addition, a large projection screen was present on which live video of students at the remote site was displayed. Finally, accommodation was present for a small group of students to follow the class locally.

At the remote site, three students could be seated. A projection screen was placed right in front of the students. The screen showed live video of the teacher and a live stream of the contents of the interactive whiteboard.

Remote students each had an individual button to enable and disable a microphone array that sends audio from the remote site to the local site. The students at the remote site could, however, neither hear nor see the students at the local site.

We saw the introduction to the PoC as an important part of the co-design session, as we wanted the participants, after discussing their ideal type of Teleclass, to be confronted with the current reality. We asked both groups of actors about their general response to the setup, to what extent it concurred with their expectations and what they saw as essential next steps for further development.

2.3 Analysis

The visual creations of the participants are in essence ambiguous; they can be interpreted in several ways. Gauntlett [6] stresses the importance of the creator's own interpretation of the artefact he or she created. Hence, the artefacts did not form our main subject of analysis. We were mainly interested in the way participants described and motivated their creations. To a certain extent, the design kit merely served as a tool to force the participants to think in more detail about the teleclass environment and to force them to consider both experiences and setup at the same time.

The descriptions that result from co-design sessions are very rich and diverse. To analyze these descriptions we followed a three-phase approach, suggested by Sleeswijk Visser and colleagues [3] in which we moved from handling the raw data, to capturing initial insights and to eventually identifying recurring and salient themes. The different team members conducted the analysis collaboratively.

Starting from the core properties of the ideal teleclass environment, named by the participants during the session, we identified main and subthemes in the descriptions.

3. Results

The co-design sessions that we organized yielded an abundance of data (i.e., the creations, participants' argumentation and remarks with regard to the Proof of Concept). Our general impression was that, although the co-design material is relatively concrete and tangible, participants handled this material in a relatively conceptual way. Their primary concern was having a rough outline of an environment (general structure, available technology and objects, ...) that would enable a desirable class experience. At this stage, the details of which particular color a wall should be in, or at which particular location a trashcan should be placed was not deemed important. This does not mean that participants did not refer to more concrete environmental or experiential aspects. The direct actors, in particular, made multiple references in this respect (e.g., having mat window-glass at the side of the hallway, so that students have natural light without outside distractions). However, these references were made in light of the bigger picture that participants were trying to build up.

As we examined the results of the co-design sessions more closely, salient and recurrent themes began to emerge. We now faced the challenge of presenting the results in a comprehensive way that was usable for further development of the teleclassroom by our project partners. On the one hand, we were conscious of the fact that the results would be potential stepping stones for the technical developers; our message had to be sufficiently clear. On the other hand, we felt that putting forth a single solution would be too restrictive. Therefore, we did not focus on the particular artefacts in the discussion with our partners. Instead, we chose to communicate three types of teleclassrooms to them that we derived from the raw data. Each type is illustrated symbolically and

described below. These high-level representations have allowed us to present our results to our project partners in such a way that the link between ideal environment and experience, as conceived by our participants, remains obvious. In addition, they permit a grounded discussion with project partners as each type has its merits and restrictions.

After presenting the different teleclassroom types, we conclude our results section with a number of general issues to take into account in the development of a teleclassroom.

3.1 Teleclassroom types

Type	Description
<p>1: Simultaneous, full interaction</p>	<p>This is a teleclassroom in which students follow a class simultaneously at two locations and there is full-fledged two-way interaction between all people involved (i.e. teacher – student interaction, student – student interaction).</p> <p>This type was proposed by some of the teachers and the indirect actors. The indirect actors envisioned a triangular/circular setup that resembles a proposition that was promoted within the Teleclassing project. In this setup both the teacher, and the students present at the other room are represented in the classroom.</p>
<p>2: Simultaneous, reduced interaction</p>	<p>This is a teleclassroom also involves simultaneous class taking, however interactivity is reduced as the focus of the setup is on supporting student-teacher interaction.</p> <p>The students participating in this project advanced this type as they did not feel a need to see students they did not know in the context of a formal lecture. Nevertheless, it is likely that they would also like to hear the questions of the local students and their respective answers, as they see the question and answer-process as an important way of increasing their understanding.</p>
<p>3: Non-simultaneous, no remote interaction</p>	<p>This is a teleclassroom in which teaching and following the class are detached in time. Students are given the freedom to take the class when, where and with whom they want. This freedom compensates for the loss of immediate interactivity.</p> <p>This type was proposed by teachers who were highly skeptical about a simultaneous teleclass. They believed that interaction would be too strongly compromised by the technology to be successful and they anticipated a heavy increase in workload.</p> <p>Students appreciated this because it enabled them to look at a class afterwards. They saw it as a convenient complementary solution.</p>

In what follows, we will discuss the teleclassroom types in more detail, treating the simultaneous setups separate from the last, non-simultaneous type. As noted before, the teleclassroom involves two distant classrooms. For the sake of clarity, we will refer to the classroom in which the teacher is physically present as the ‘local site’. The other classroom is referred to as the ‘remote site’.

a. Simultaneous teleclass setups

The main difference between the two simultaneous setups is whether or not students at the two sites are able to have remote contact with each other. It is noteworthy, however, that participants' argumentation for representing students at the other site or not, was highly similar. Both proponents and opponents of representing students argued that quality of education would benefit from implementing the choice they defended.

The participants arguing in favor of a Type 1-setup believed it would be better to make the other students visible, since it would allow for social control among the students between both sites. It was thought that feeling both the presence of the other students and the teacher at the remote site would improve concentration and hence the information transfer from teacher to student. To enhance this sense of presence, some indirect actors suggested using a similar interior and acoustics in both classrooms, which would support the illusion of 'being together'.

Students were the main proponents for the Type 2-setup. When asked why they did not represent the students at the other site in their solution, students said that they did not feel a need to interact with students at the other site or to get to know them. Given that seeing and hearing the remote students had no added value, the representation of students at the other site could only be distracting from what was essential to them: clearly perceiving the teacher and teaching material. Only when a student at the other side would ask a question, some sort of representation of this student seemed necessary.

In relation to both types, three big issues were discussed:

- Realism

A recurring discussion throughout the sessions, mainly related to the simultaneous setup, was to what extent the experience at the remote site should be 'realistic'. Some participants argued that students at the remote site should have the feeling that they are in the same room with the people at the local site. They considered a truthful representation of the local site to be vital for remote students to feel involved with that site. Others held the opinion that how the local site is conveyed to and experienced at the remote site might have to be adjusted (i.e., deviate from what is realistic) to ensure good quality of education at both the local and the remote site.

In essence, the Type 1 setup seems to fit the discourse of those arguing for a highly realistic solution. In its perfect realization, the Type 1 teleclass environment would give all user involved the impression that they are actually in the same room. In its ideal form, this setup would visually resemble a single physical setting as closely as possible and therefore be as realistic as possible. In contrast, for the Type 2 setup, the reduced experience of the activities at the local site can be seen as an adjustment of the 'reality' of the local site.

Although Type 1 is more in line with the 'realistic' discourse, it must be noted that arguments for realism and adjustment came up in participants' reflections on both types of environments. In relation to Type 1, for instance, it was discussed whether the smells of the one site should be communicated to the other site, most of the participants being opposed to the idea. Also, even though Type 2 is in essence less realistic, it was also argued by some students that the teacher should be real-life sized. So the setup types cannot be clearly attributed to either the realistic or the 'adjusted' discourse.

- Interaction

Having students asking questions is a complex issue in a teleclass setting. All participants agreed that both the students at the local and the remote site should have the opportunity to ask questions, as this benefits the

students' understanding of the class material. But while the threshold to ask questions should be low, the opportunity to ask questions should also be under the control of the teacher to avoid chaos. Several suggestions were made: using an intercom system, using personal technology such as laptops or mobile phones to send written questions or providing unrestricted audio transmission. However, the two latter suggestions were thought to be too difficult to manage. In the end, the former suggestion seemed most favorable and preferable to the existing traditional solution of passing on a microphone.

Additionally, an important worry of both direct and indirect actors was how to enable interaction that differed from the formal lecture type. For example, students often make use of the class break to ask questions to teachers. When thinking about how this interaction should be supported between a student at a remote site and a teacher at a local site, participants did not find a solution to support this typically spontaneous and informal kind of interaction. Teachers would have difficulty treating both student groups equally. Furthermore, when prioritizing the students at the remote site, teachers might feel compelled to stay in the classroom and would have little opportunity to take a break themselves. Similarly, participants were concerned about how more dynamic classes, such as group work or practical classes, would be supported. Indeed, our educational system is evolving towards increased use of more dynamic didactic models. It is still to be seen how these types of lessons can be organized from a distance. This issue is related to the next point of discussion.

- Flexibility

Flexibility with regard to a teleclass environment can be interpreted in several ways. It was noted that a teleclass environment should be flexible so that it is versatile: a single classroom should allow both teaching and taking lessons at a distance. Also, ideally it can accommodate more than two sites. Finally, as was noted in the previous paragraph, several participants argued that the ideal teleclass environment should support different types of educational formats, as formal lectures are losing importance. Some argued that a teleclass environment would achieve ultimate flexibility when it would be detached from both time and space. This characteristic is closely related to a Type 3 teleclass environment, and is discussed in more detail below.

b. Non-simultaneous teleclass setup

This setup was especially advocated by the teachers who were skeptical of the simultaneous setup, fearing that these setups would interfere too strongly with their teaching style. They did not want to be confused by activities going on at the remote site, having to deal too much with technicalities, nor did they feel like having to worry about whether everything is functioning at the remote site. For them, making recordings of lessons available to students was seen as least intrusive. They felt this setup would benefit students as well, as this would enable them to take classes in their own time, where and with whom they wanted.

The students agreed on these advantages, but did not see this setup as a full alternative to the synchronous setups; they perceived the asynchronous setup as a supplement, an additional service to it. This increased flexibility in both time and space that this setup offered was seen as an enormous gain, and in some cases could compensate for the loss of interactivity.

This form of 'blended learning', using both simultaneous and non-simultaneous educational settings, does not offer a solution for those teachers who were skeptical of a simultaneous setup, but gives students additional freedom and the 'best of both worlds'.

3.2 Caveats

Apart from the issues related to these specific setups, some general concerns and suggestions were also expressed during the sessions that should be considered as important caveats in the development of the teleclassroom.

A first set of concerns has to do with the **ease of use** and the **reliability** of the technology: if there is a steep learning curve for a particular technology, teachers will be prone to reject it. For instance, one of the teachers explained how he had attempted to use an interactive whiteboard, but when he found out that he had to download software first and that he had to choose from many options, he gave up. Teachers also want to be assured that everything is working fine, so this implies a need for feedback, so that they are sure that everything is being shown that is supposed to be shown. However, the ease of use also has to do with the impact of the technology on the teaching style of the teacher. For instance, many teachers prefer to walk around during class to increase contact with the students and get them more involved. When a camera system forces them to stand still, this might be a barrier in using the technology.

In this regard, some experts have referred to this as making the technology **transparent**, making it invisible for the direct actors. The ideal they had in mind was that the direct actors would not have to worry or think about the technology at all, would not even realize it is there. However, it is also clear that the direct actors, in particular the teachers, need to have some control over the technology, for instance when allowing students to ask questions and interrupt the lecture. Hence, full transparency would probably not be an ideal the direct actors strive for.

A second set of recommendations has to do with the **services** surrounding the teleclass setting. The teachers asked for some training before using the technology, not only from a technological viewpoint, but also from an educational point. They also expected that teachers needed to be sensitized to make the leap towards using the technology. There was also worry about the maintenance of the teleclass environment and whether there would be assistance if problems were to arise. These issues can seem trivial from an architect's point of view, but they are important in the conception of the setting and the teleclass environment. These are issues that are elementary for direct actors and largely determine how they will experience the setting.

The same goes for the quality of the **classroom** itself. All direct actors mentioned the importance of ergonomic furniture, good lighting, air quality, having Internet access, being able to easily use multimedia, the reduction of noise and the availability of food and drinks. These are important elements to take into account in an early phase of the design phase, as they largely determine how the end users will feel in the rooms.

4. Discussion

4.1 Course of the sessions

Since co-designing for environments is a new branch of the field of participative design, we have developed a new toolkit that would be suitable for all the stakeholders we wanted to involve in the research. Beforehand, we were not entirely sure if the sessions would result in the type of information we were looking for. However, looking back, our opinion is that our approach worked very well, and yielded a huge amount of information and insights.

It was remarkable to see how the participants used the content of the kit very differently. The indirect users or experts had a tendency to use the open-ended material rather than the words and pictures. They preferred working on the flipchart pages right away, drawing setups and exploring ideas, and had to be encouraged to use the experiential material. The direct users however, preferred using the experiential material such as pictures and the words, and ended with thinking about the setup of the room. While this difference in working methods is to be expected given the different backgrounds of the participants, it is also a point of attention for the researchers conducting the sessions to actively encourage the participants to think about the connection between experience and setup.

The analyses of the data retrieved from these sessions is a challenge, and as we said, the three types of teleclass environments we presented are the result of interpretation, even though they more or less followed literally from the sessions. Which of these types should be realized depends not only on the end users, but also on policy makers, the educational material being used, the educational format that is chosen, etc. To make the model less generic, additional iterations should take place, further bridging the experience and setup of a teleclass.

Letting the actors first think about the teleclass setting, and then confronting them with the current setting proved to be very insightful, as it enabled them look critically at the setup. On the other hand, this also had as an effect that the big difference between their ideal vision and the current reality led to a mild disappointment with the current setup, that was still very technology oriented and had paid limited attention to the experience the users wished for. This approach led the participants to look more critical at the Proof of concept, which benefits the quality of the design recommendations that follow from the sessions.

4.2 The wider potential of teleclasses

During the co-design sessions, participants started thinking about the broader implications teleclass environments might have for students. Especially what we have previously called 'blended learning', opened perspectives towards an increased mobility of students. The 'blended learning' model would allow them to more easily follow lessons that normally are not part of their curriculum. It could widen their scope by letting them participate in a wider range of classes and even allow them to take classes that are not offered by their university. Of course, this potential of teleclassrooms is mainly dependant on the extent to which the academic world will embrace this potential.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we described how we developed a new design toolkit to make both direct and indirect actors with very different backgrounds think about the same problem. Their main challenge was to consider the experiences that were needed in a teleclass environment, and how those can be translated to a specific setup. The sessions resulted in three conceptual setups and a number of caveats with regard to teleclassrooms.

In our discussion of the three setups, we have not made a prioritization. This is in line with our aim of the co-design sessions. The co-design sessions served to illustrate the spectrum of possible teleclass setups. Therefore, we have not put forth a final solution or provided a restrictive set of recommendations. By describing each type of teleclass, with its own set of (dis)advantages, our main goal was to inspire developers rather than to restrict them. This also entailed making them aware of issues that they were not necessarily aware of.

Importantly, the results of our sessions have put the original vision of the Teleclassing project into perspective. Realism can be useful, but an immersive and realistic experience of being in the same classroom should not be pursued at all cost. An adjusted representation of what is happening at the distant location may be preferred to a fully realistic representation. Interactivity is important for educational reasons, but it also raises extra complexities for teachers, who need to stay in control of the classroom, whether that is a teleclassroom or not. And finally the setup should allow for the flexibility that is needed given the complexity of academic education. Ultimately, a certain detachment of time and place, allowing students to follow lessons simultaneously at several locations but also allowing them to take the lessons own time, has potential for all actors involved. Even though additional iterations are required to further shape the teleclassroom, it is also clear that the evolution of teleclasses, and the enormous potential they hold for all actors involved, especially students, will depend on to what extent universities will embrace the potential of this new technology.

6. Acknowledgement

The Interdisciplinary Institute for Broadband Technology (IBBT) is gratefully acknowledged for financing the research described in this paper in the context of the project 'Teleclassing' (<http://www.ibbt.be/en/project/teleclassing>).

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